
The Issue of Financing Material-Architectural Culture in the History of the Kokan Khan

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Abstract: The article contains information about the financial system of the Kokan Khanate, mainly the history of construction and ancient monuments. The economic basis of the construction of a mosque, madrasa, ditch, caravanserai, and bazaars in the khanate has been analyzed.

Key words: Khan, finance, money, treasury, madrasa, mosque.

In the analysis of the financial system of the Kokand Khanate, attention was paid to the construction of material architectural monuments based on the income of the country's treasury. The historical buildings built by the khans who ruled the state since the establishment of the Kokand Khanate, that is, from 1709, were analyzed based on the sources. Each scientific research has its own characteristics, and the circumstances that hindered the proof of the material value of constructions and the basis of construction funds in financial matters were the following:

- Almost all the sources that serve to illuminate the history of the Kokand Khanate have information about who built the monument, but its financial support is not provided;
- All the documents related to the cabinet of the Koqan khans stored in the National Archives of Uzbekistan belong to the last period of Khudoyor Khan's rule, and the documents of the previous period have not been preserved to this day.
- Even in the documents kept in UzMA, the construction of the monuments is not given in full, among the texts, during the research of some notes at the end of the documents, some evidence was found;
- In sources, the number of historical monuments is extremely large, but today there are few monuments preserved in the city of Ko'kan and the territory of the khanate, and they were demolished for certain reasons;

In the study of the history of the construction industry of the Kokand Khanate, it was analyzed into the following groups:

- Buildings of the administrative system - the khan's palace, i.e. the army, the arch, the cabinet, the army of the governor or the beg.
- Constructions related to the military system - for example, a fortress, a wall, a reserve.
- Material buildings specific to the religious sphere - mosque, mosque, dalailkhana, qalandarkhana, etc.;
- Buildings related to the educational system - for example, madrasas, schools are included in this category.
- Buildings related to the trade system - market, shop, stall, shops.
- Buildings related to the field of service (service) - bathhouse, barbershop, mill, barber shop

- citizens' immovable property - house, yard, garden yard.
- engineering buildings and structures - bridges, canals, canals, cisterns, dams are examples.

According to historical sources, the buildings built in the Kokand Khanate in the 19th century were built by khans, queens, nobles in the state administration, i.e. princes and officials, people who gained prestige in the military field - tycoons and rich investors.

Niyaz Muhammad Shakhruhbi's zikr statement: "He built the city of Kokan and turned it into the capital of his kingdom. He engaged in charitable works and built madrasahs and mosques. He built a high castle in the south of the city, which is now called Tefa fortress. There is no sign of that high castle now..." - proves that financial attention was paid to construction works from the first period of establishment of the khanate, that is, from 1709.

The sources of the construction work during Erdonabi's time were also researched: "When Erdona Khan returned from Oratepa to Khoqand, the capital of the kingdom, he was occupied with justice and honesty. . The next year, he dug a big river from the Sokh river and brought it to the registon of the Syrdarya. Many villages and settlements have prospered from this food. Now this food is known as Naimancha.[Sh.V.360] Erdanabi built a palace, and the information about it is given in the following form: Erdona Khan left the Amirlik Palace to the heirs of the Highness and ordered to build a high palace in the middle of the city. Architects quickly built a high palace building on the site of the current Sultan Murad madrasa. In this palace, in 1177/1763, the royal crown was placed on the head of Humayun, and the throne of command was adorned with his blessed body."

Sh. Vakhidov lists Umar Khan, Muhammad Ali Khan, Khudoyar Khan, Nadirabegim from the princesses, Sultan Muradbek, Sultan Sayyid Khan from the bek or princes, Muslim Qul, Alimquli, Khalmuhammed thousandbashi from the military officials.

In the history of the Kokand Khanate, among the examples of material culture, the building of a madrasa, mosque, takyakhana, karakhana, cistern, bridge, and bazaars ranked next to the construction of an ark, i.e., a palace. The money of the palace treasury was used mainly for the construction, repair and equipment of the luxurious arches of the ruler. It is noted in the sources that the construction of madrasahs in the Khanate was accelerated during the periods of Norbotabi, Olim Khan, and Umar Khan.[1] But there is no clear evidence on the basis of which they were built. For example, if we take the Madrasah of Norbotabi, this monument still serves as the main Friday mosque in the city of Koqan. According to the information about the history of its construction, it can be known that Norbotabi's mother gave her precious jewelry belonging to her dowry and said that she wanted to build a madrasa, and because Norbotabi was personally the head of this work, it got the name "Norbotabi madrasa".

During Umar Khan's time, mosques and madrasahs were built in Kokan, Tashkent, Turkestan, Shymkent, Sayram, Avliyoota, and cemeteries were organized.[Sh.V 340-b]. "With his great zeal, Sharif built a lot of buildings and buildings from his current donations. Among them, ankhor dug from Syrdarya to Shahrikhan, Khan arig' in Tashkent district. These anchors are still used by the inhabitants of many villages. Madrasay Oliy and Jome mosque in the middle of Khoqand city are also a monument to him. Even better buildings of his emirs and ministers have survived to our time, and their number cannot be contained in this brief work.

Based on the sources, it is not difficult to estimate that during the reign of Muhammad Ali Khan, construction costs were large. "Many buildings and current charity structures remain from the time of Muhammadali Khan. Including Khan's madrasa, the second madrasa in Ohangaron neighborhood. Khan's mother also built a madrasa, a reading room for the permanent residence of kalomullah hafiz, and appointed many endowments for each of them. Until now, they are full of seekers of Shari'i sciences. During his rule, his emirs and ministers in Fergana country repaired mosques and madrasahs, charitable buildings, and allocated many endowments for these structures, many of which are still in existence and valid. Students of Ahle Islam are enjoying using them. It would be too long to describe them in detail in this summary. [455].

In the work of Ibrat ul-Khavaqin, the information that Khudoyar Khan asked to build a madrasa in the will of his mother is given as follows: ""the last madrasa Volidai Khan Zaman, that is, the late Hokimoyim, bequeathed to Khudoyor Khan before his death. Following the will, (Khudoyor Khan) built a higher madrasa on the east side of the mosque. His history was found by one of the noble people as "mazhari ulama" [page 120 a].

We think that certain financial resources (jewelry or money) were mentioned in the will, and Hokim wanted his wealth to be spent on good deeds in order to be rewarded in the future. It is possible to know from the next information that proves this opinion that the will was fulfilled: "After the Khan got rid of these affairs, he was busy with justice and the improvement of the country. He dug large canals from the Sokh and Hushyor rivers and built good villages and settlements. Including building the Mingoyim madrasa, which still exists today and is full of students, and many endowments were allocated to it. This madrasa was built by the khan's wife Mingoyim. If we describe the buildings and other charitable works built during the age of this righteous khan, our words will be long and we can get away from the goal".

There are a lot of information about the construction of madrasas in the sources related to the history of the Kokand Khanate. "In the same year, Hazrat Sahib opened the Khanaqah stage in the south of his madrasah, expanded it further and built a museum. It was the year 1284/1867-68, when Khudoyor Khan built and organized the market stalls, the palace palace, the cotton palace and the cotton capon. The history of these buildings was found by one of the elegant people of that time, he wrote an essay about Khudoyar Khan in the form of hymns and odes, and drew it into verse.

Among the princes, it should be noted that Nasriddinbek spent a lot of money on construction works. "Khudoyor Khan carried out unprecedented large constructions during the third khanate and encouraged his son Nasriddinbek and his relatives to do the same. One of the first things he did in the palace of Andijan was to establish a special school in the palace for the education of the children of the palace and other officials, like his father. In addition to this school, he built a magnificent madrasa and mosque in Andijan. During his governorship, a gunpowder manufacturing enterprise in the village of Choykent near Andijan city, as well as European rifle and other weapon repair enterprises in the city, will be expanded and rebuilt.

In conclusion, it can be said that the funds allocated for construction works from the financial system of the Kokand Khanate were not clearly mentioned in the works of local historians, and the documents of UzNA refer to the last years of the state, so it was not possible to fully reveal the research. Nevertheless, the analysis of some aspects of the issue will serve for future studies that will allow a deep study of the history of this country.

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